

Role of dyes as energy materials in photogalvanic conversion of solar energy

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Abstract : The comparative performance of photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion and storage reported by using Lissamine green B, Bromocresol green and Brilliant blue FCF as different photosensitizers with ascorbic acid as reductant and sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) as surfactant in different systems. The photogeneration of photopotential are 850.0, 834.0 and 810.0 mV whereas the photocurrent at equilibrium are 375.0, 350.0 and 445.0 μ A, respectively. The observed conversion efficiencies for Lissamine green B, Bromocresol green and Brilliant blue FCF with ascorbic acid-sodium lauryl sulphate systems are 1.0257, 0.8030 and 1.1592%, respectively. The fill factors 0.2598, 0.2283 and 0.2643 are experimentally determined at the power point of the cell where the absolute value is 1.0. The effects of different parameters on the electrical output of the cell are observed and current-voltage (i-V) characteristics of the cell were studied in detail.

Keywords : Lissamine green B (LG B), Bromocresol green (BC G), Brilliant blue FCF (BB FCF), photogalvanic effect, conversion efficiency.

Introduction

As natural resources are being exhausted at ever-increasing pace and when all natural resources of energy will be completely exhausted then man will have no other alternative then to utilize solar energy. It is not only new, harmless and low cost source of energy but also this inexhaustible source of energy. Although society's electricity needs are largely continuous, clouds and darkness dictate that photovoltaic solar cells have an intermittent output. In this regard, photogalvanic cells hold great promises to address both issues simultaneously, by producing electricity by solar energy conversion.

Becquerel¹ was the first to observe the flow of current between the unsymmetrical illuminated metal electrodes in sunlight, and the photogalvanics was first reported by Rideal and Williams², but it was systematically investigated by Rabinowitch^{3,4}. Later on Kaneko and Yamada⁵, Murthy *et al.*⁶, Rohatgi-Mukherjee *et al.*⁷, Folcher and Paris⁸, Alfredo *et al.*⁹, Dube *et al.*¹⁰, Bayer *et al.*¹¹, Matsumoto *et al.*¹² and Shiroishi *et al.*¹³ have studied some interesting photogalvanic systems. Bisquert *et al.*¹⁴ have reviewed the physical-chemical principles of dye-sensitized solar cells, whereas Mayer¹⁵ has presented the molecular approaches to solar energy conversion. The

problems encountered in the development of photogalvanic cells have been discussed from time to time. Krasnoholovets *et al.*¹⁶, Madhwani *et al.*¹⁷, Gangotri and Bhimwal¹⁸, Genwa and Chouhan¹⁹ and Genwa and Sagar²⁰ have recently developed some photogalvanic systems for solar energy conversion and storage. The scientific community has successfully converted solar energy in electrical energy up to desired extent through various processes but storage capacity of solar energy is still not up to the mark to use it as and when required. Many of them have used different photosensitizers, surfactants, reductants in photogalvanic cells, but no attention has been paid to the use of these three systems containing three different dyes as energy materials to enhance the electrical output and performance of the photogalvanic cells. Therefore, the present work was undertaken to achieve better performance and commercial viability of the photogalvanic cells.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of dyes, reductant and surfactant concentration :

The photogalvanic effect was studied in photogalvanic cell containing three dyes; Lessamine green B, Bromocresol green and Brilliant blue FCF in the presence of reductant ascorbic acid and anionic surfactant NaLS.

The concentration of dyes were kept $2.8 \times 10^{-5} M$, $1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in LG B-ascorbic acid-NaLS, BC G-ascorbic acid-NaLS and BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS systems, respectively. It was observed that there was an increase in photopotential and photocurrent on increasing the concentration of dye. It was felt necessary to keep the concentration of dyes $10^{-5} M$ for effective results in electrical output. Lower concentration range of dyes, there will be limited number of dyes molecules to absorb major portion of the light in path and, therefore, there is low electrical output whereas higher concentration of dyes will not permit the desired light intensity to reach the molecules near the electrodes and hence, corresponding fall in the power of the cell was observed.

Ascorbic acid used as reductant in photogalvanic cell. The concentration of reductant were kept $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1.1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in LG B-ascorbic acid-NaLS, BC G-Ascorbic acid-NaLS and BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS systems, respectively.

With increase in concentration of the reductant, the electric output of photogalvanic cell was found to increase until it reaches on maximum value then there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent both on further increasing the concentration of reductant. The fall in power output was also resulted with decrease in concentration of reductant due to less number of molecules available for electron donation to the dye molecule. On the other hand, the large concentration of reductant again resulted into a decrease in electrical output because the large number of reductant molecules hindered by the dye molecules reaching the electrode in desired time limit.

Reductant concentration also affects the cell output. With the increase in concentration of the reductant [Ascorbic acid], the photopotential and photocurrent were found to increase until it reaches a maximum value. On further increase in concentration of ascorbic acid, a decrease in the electrical output of the cells was observed. The fall in power output was also resulted with decrease in concentration of reductant due to less number of molecules available for electron donation to the cationic form of dye. On the other hand, the movement of dye molecules hindered by the higher concentration of reductant to reach the electrode in the desired time limit and it will also result in to a decrease in electrical output.

An anionic surfactant, sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) was used in all three systems. The concentration of surfactant was kept $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$, $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ in LG B-ascorbic acid-NaLS, BC G-ascorbic acid-NaLS and BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS systems, respectively. It was found that electrical output of the cell increase on increasing the surfactant concentration reaching a maximum value. On further increase in concentration of surfactant a fall in electrical output was observed. The most important properties of micellar systems are the ability to solubilize a variety of molecules and substantial catalytic effect on many chemical reactions. The better electrical output of the photogalvanic cell was observed around the critical micelle concentration of the surfactant. Photoinduced electron transfer processes in micellar systems are potentially important for efficient energy conversion and storage, because surfactants help to achieve the separate photoproducts by hydrophilic-hydrophobic interaction of the products with the micellar interface. Micelles not only solubilized the photosensitizer molecules to a maximum extent around their CMC values but have stabilized also the photogalvanic cell systems.

Effect of pH :

Photogalvanic cells containing Lissamine green B-ascorbic acid-NaLS system, Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system and Brilliant blue FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS system were found to be quite sensitive to pH of the solution. It was observed that all the three systems with three different dyes works effectively in strong alkaline range. The working range for the present work was in pH range of 11.52–12.80. The potential of the system was found to increase as the pH was increased. The potential reached to a maximum value for a particular pH and then decreased on further increase in pH. It was observed that pH for optimum condition for reductant has a relation with its pKa value i.e. the desired pH should be slightly higher than their pKa values ($pH > pK_a$). The reason may be the availability of reductant in its anionic form, which is better donor form.

Effect of diffusion length and electrode area :

The diffusion length (i.e. the distance between SCE and platinum electrode) greatly affects all the three systems. The effect of variation of diffusion length on the electrical output (i_{max} , i_{eq}) and initial rate of generation of

current of the photogalvanic cell was observed by using the H-cell of different dimensions. It was observed that in the first few minutes of illumination there was a sharp increase in the photocurrent and then there was a gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. This behaviour of photocurrent indicates an initial rapid reaction followed by a slow rate-determining step. The results are also discussed to know about electroactive species by considering various probable processes and combinations form electroactive species for the electrical output of the photogalvanic cells. These processes and combinations are summarized in Table 1. If the oxidized form of the reductant is formed only in the illuminated chamber and it is considered to be the electroactive species in the dark cham-

ber, then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to accept an electron from the electrode. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of generation of photocurrent should decrease with an increase in diffusion length, but it is not observed experimentally. The value of (i_{eq}) is also observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length (rather it decreases slightly). On the basis of the effect of diffusion path length on the current parameters, it may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi-leuco form of dye (photosensitizers) and the dye in the illuminated and the dark chamber, respectively (Table 1). However, the reductant and its oxidized product act only as electron carriers in the path.

The effect of electrode area on current parameters was also observed in the three systems and observations have been given in Table 2. Based on observations it was observed that the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) was found to increase on increasing the electrode area but the equilibrium photocurrent (i_{eq}) was affected slightly, rather it was decreased slightly.

Effect of light intensity :

The intensity of light was also affects the electrical output of the cell. It was observed that photocurrent shows a linear increasing behavior with the increase in light intensity whereas photo potential increased in logarithmic manner. This increasing behavior of electrical output due to increase in number of photons with increase in light intensity (Fig. 1(a,b,c)).

i-V Characteristics :

The open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current (i_{sc}) of the photogalvanic cells were measured under the

Table 1. Probable process and combinations for electroactive species

In illuminated chamber	In dark chamber
Dye (D)	Oxidized form of the reductant (R ⁺)
Semi or leuco form of the dye (D ⁻)	Oxidized form of the reductant (R ⁺)
Semi or leuco form of the dye (D ⁻)	Dye (D)

ber, then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to accept an electron from the electrode. As a consequence, the maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of generation of photocurrent should decrease with an increase in diffusion length, but it is not observed

Table 2. Effect of electrode area

Electrode area (cm ⁻²)	Lissamine green B-ascorbic acid-NaLS system		Bromocresol green-ascorbic acid-NaLS system		Brilliant blue FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS system	
	i_{max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)	i_{max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)	i_{max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)
0.70	428.0	383.0	428.0	362.0	504.0	459.0
0.85	436.0	379.0	435.0	355.0	513.0	452.0
1.00	445.0	375.0	440.0	350.0	520.0	445.0
1.15	454.0	372.0	446.0	342.0	527.0	438.0
1.30	462.0	368.0	452.0	335.0	535.0	432.0

i_{max} (μA) = Maximum photocurrent and i_{eq} (μA) = equilibrium photocurrent.
 LG B-ascorbic acid-NaLS system; Lissamine green B = $2.8 \times 10^{-5} M$, ascorbic acid = $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M$, NaLS = $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ and pH = 12.58.
 BC G-ascorbic acid-NaLS system; Bromocresol green = $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$, ascorbic acid = $1.1 \times 10^{-3} M$, NaLS = $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and pH = 11.60.
 BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS system; Brilliant blue FCF = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, ascorbic acid = $3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, NaLS = $1.6 \times 10^{-3} M$ and pH = 12.58.
 Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} , Temperature = 303 K.

Fig. 1. (a,b,c) Variation of photocurrent and log V with light intensity.

continuous illumination of light, with the help of digital pH meter (keeping the circuit open) and a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed) respectively. The potential and current in between these two extreme values (V_{pp} and i_{pp}) were recorded with the help of a carbon pot (log 407 K) connected in the circuit of microammeter through which an external load applied. i-V characteristics of the cells are shown in current-potential curve (Fig. 2 (a,b,c)).

It was observed that i-V curve deviated from its regular rectangular shape. A point in the i-V curve, called

Fig. 2. (a,b,c) Current-voltage (i-V) curves of the cell.

power point (pp), was determined where the product of curve of current and potential was maximum. With the help of i-V curve, the fill-factor was calculated by using the formula

$$\text{Fill-factor } (\eta) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

Cell performance and conversion efficiency :

The performance of the photogalvanic cell was observed by applying an external load (necessary to have

current at power point) after termination the illumination as soon as the potential reaches a constant value. The performance was determined in terms of the $t_{1/2}$ i.e. the time required in fall of the output (power) to its half value at power point. The overall comparative performance of the photogalvanic cells was observed and reached to remarkable level with respect to electrical output, initial generation of photocurrent, conversion efficiency and storage capacity of the photogalvanic cell. The comparative performance obtained in all the three systems is summarized in Table 3 and graphically shown in time-power curve (Fig. 3 (a,b,c)).

Conversion efficiency of the cell was determined by using the formula :

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{A \times 10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Cell reactions :

When certain dyes are excited by the light in the presence of electron donating substance (reductant), are rapidly changed into colourless form. The dye now acts as a powerful reducing agent and can donate electron to other substance and reconverted to its oxidized state²¹. Scheme of mechanism²² is shown in Fig. 4.

Illumination chamber :

On irradiation, dye molecule get excited :

The excited dye molecule accepts an electron from reductant and converted into semi or leuco form of dye and the reductant into its excited state :

At platinum electrode :

The semi or leuco form of dye loses an electron and converted into original dye molecule :

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode :

Finally semi/leuco form of dye and oxidized form of reductant combine to give original dye and reductant molecule and the cycle will go on :

Here Dye, Dye*, Dye⁻, R and R⁺ are the dye, its excited form, leuco form, reductant and its oxidized form, respectively.

Table 3. Comparison of photoelectric parameters of three systems

Electrical Parameters	Observed values		
	LG B-ascorbic acid-NaLS system	BG-ascorbic acid-NaLS system	BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS system
1. Open circuit voltage, V_{oc} (mV)	1095.0	1045.0	1025.0
2. Photopotential, ΔV (mV)	850.0	834.0	810.0
3. Maximum photocurrent, i_{max} (μA)	445.0	440.0	520.0
4. Short circuit current, i_{sc} (μA)	375.0	350.0	445.0
5. Equilibrium photo current, i_{eq} (μA)	375.0	350.0	445.0
6. Current at power point, i_{pp} (μA)	210.0	180.0	220.0
7. Potential at power point, V_{pp} (mV)	508.0	464.0	548.0
8. Power at power point (μW)	106.68	83.52	120.56
9. Rate of generation of current ($\mu A \text{ min}^{-1}$)	15.89	11.58	15.31
10. Charging time (min)	130.0	160.0	140.0
11. Fill-factor (η)	0.2598	0.2283	0.2643
12. Conversion efficiency (%)	1.0257	0.8030	1.1592
13. $t_{1/2}$ (min)	170.0	140.0	130.0

Fig. 3. (a,b,c) Time-power curves of the cell.

Fig. 4. Scheme of cell reactions.

Conclusions

World is facing energy crisis in present time and to meet the energy demand is challenge to nation. There is urgent need to search a renewable device, which can be used, for energy conversion and storage for maximum time. An effort has been made through this work with the use of three dyes (Lissamine green B, Bromocresol green and Brilliant blue FCF) in photogalvanic cell system and appreciable results were obtained. The electrical parameters of three systems were observed using reducing agent (ascorbic acid). The effect of pH and concentration of reductant, surfactant, dye and effect of diffusion length, temperature, and light intensity on electrical parameter of the cell were studied in detail. On the basis of results obtained, it may be concluded that efficient photogalvanic cell can be fabricated with the use of BB FCF-ascorbic acid-NaLS system in view of both storage capacity and conversion efficiency.

Materials and methods :

Lissamine green B (Loba Chemie, Mumbai), Bromocresol green (Loba Chemie, Mumbai) and Brilliant blue FCF (Ases Chemical, Jodhpur), ascorbic acid (Ases Chemical, Jodhpur), NaLS (Sisco Research Laboratories, Mumbai) and sodium hydroxide (RFCL, New Delhi) were used in the present work. Solutions of ascorbic acid, Bromocresol green, NaLS and NaOH (1 N) were prepared in double distilled water (conductivity $3.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Sm}^{-1}$) and kept in amber coloured containers to protect them from sun light. Structures of dyes are shown in Schemes 1, 2 and 3.

Scheme 1. Lissamine green B.

A mixture of dye, reductant (ascorbic acid), surfactant (NaLS) and NaOH solution was taken in an H-type glass tube which was blackened by black carbon paper to unaffected from sun radiation. A shiny platinum foil electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) was immersed in one limb of the H-

Scheme 2. Bromocresol green.

Scheme 3. Brilliant blue FCF.

tube and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was immersed in the other limb. Platinum electrode acts as a working electrode and SCE as a counter electrode. The whole system was first placed in the dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing the platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips). A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiation. Photochemical bleaching of the dye was studied potentiometrically. Absorption spectrum of dye-surfactant combination was noted by using Spectrophotometer (Systronics 106) with the matched pair of silica cuvettes (path length 1 cm). All spectral measurements were duplicated in a constant temperature water bath maintained with in ± 1 °C and mean values were processed for data analysis.

A digital pH meter (Systronics 335) was used to measure the potential and a microammeter (Nucon) was used to measure the current generated by the system respectively. The current voltage characteristics were studied by applying an external load with the help of a carbon pot

(log 470 K) connected in the circuit.

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